

The Impact of Family Environment and Students Discipline for the Result of Economics Subject Grade XI SMA Negeri 5 Pematang Siantar Year 2023/2024

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ABSTRACT

This type of research is quantitative research with a quantitative descriptive data analysis approach with the testing media used is Microsoft Excel . The total population in this study was 102 students. The sample collection technique used was the Slovin formula. The data collection technique used was a questionnaire. Hypothesis data collection techniques use simple regression analysis , multiple regression analysis and coefficient of determination (R²). The results of this research state that: 1) There is a positive and significant influence of the family environment on learning outcomes, this result can be seen in the t test where the calculated t value of learning discipline (0, 0 8) > t table value (1.318) which means the variable is significant. Mukticolinearity Test . The assumption of Tolerance or Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) is capable stated that If VIF > 10 or mark Tolerance < 1.20 so that capable multicollinearity., or If VIF < 10 or mark Tolerance > 0.10 so it is not capable of multicollinearity. It can be seen in the attachment, (1.20) that Tolerance > 0.10 or Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) < 10, so it can be concluded that the data is not capable of symptoms of multicollinearity

INTRODUCTION

Education is one of the important things that has become a necessity of life. One can learn many things through education. One of them is learning to form a good personality. This is in accordance with the essence of education contained in the Law of the Republic of Indonesia no. 20 of 2003 concerning "National Education System" Article 1 Paragraph 1.

With the existence of this law, from time to time education must become a priority and become an orientation for efforts to develop it, both in terms of facilities and infrastructure, as well as in terms of materials and achievements. In formal education, learning shows positive changes so that at the final stage, new skills, abilities and knowledge will be obtained. The results of the learning process are reflected in learning outcomes. These changes in behavior are obtained after students complete their learning program through interaction with various learning resources and the learning environment. "Learning outcomes are behavior that can be observed and show a person's abilities. Students' abilities which are behavioral treatments as a result of learning can be classified into certain dimensions. These learning outcomes are a standard for progress in the quality of education in schools, because student learning outcomes are an indicator of the quality of education in schools.

Economics learning outcomes are influenced by various factors, namely factors originating from within the student and those originating from outside the student. Factors within the student (internal) can be in the form of physical condition, intelligence, creativity, motivation, discipline, talent, learning style , and also the student's own attitude towards the teacher and subject matter. Meanwhile, factors from outside the student can include factors from family, environment, educators, school, and also peers. These factors influence economic learning outcomes directly and indirectly.

Family environmental factors are one of the strong external factors that can influence economic learning outcomes. Children will receive influence from the family in the form of: "The way parents educate children, the relationships between family members, the household atmosphere and the family's economic situation." If these factors in the family can carry out their respective functions and roles well, they will be able to create situations and conditions that can encourage children to study more actively. Parents who pay little/no attention to their children's education, for example they are indifferent to their children's learning, do not pay attention at all to their children's interests and needs in learning, do not organize their study time, do not provide/equip their learning tools, do not pay attention to whether their children are learning. or not, not wanting to know how their child's learning progress is, the difficulties they experience in learning and so on, can cause children to not/be less successful in their studies.

Learning Discipline that influences Learning Achievement includes Study Discipline at home and Study Discipline at school. Many of the mutually agreed rules are violated, such as cheating on tests, being late for school, ignoring assigned assignments, and so on. One of the things that underlies learning discipline is the emergence of students' awareness of being willing to carry out and complete the tasks given, and also study in an orderly manner, without coercion from other parties.

Based on observations made at SMA Negeri 5 Pematang Siantar, discipline is one of the personal factors that can influence student achievement of learning outcomes. The discipline applied tends to be lacking, so students tend to be lazy about studying, and this ultimately affects their learning outcomes. And supervision of student learning activities also tends to be minimal. The only thing parents ask at home

is what their child's test score is. But ignoring the learning process at home. However, for students who are more fortunate, they have older brothers or sisters, who sometimes teach them about material they don't yet understand in Economics. Student learning outcomes can be measured using economics test results. The benchmark for student success, especially Class

From the description above, there are still some students whose grades have not reached the KKM. This is influenced by various factors such as students' lack of learning discipline, family environmental factors that still do not support their children's learning continuity. Thus, it is clear that student learning discipline and the family environment play a role in education in general, and in achieving learning achievement in particular. Based on the description of the background to the problem, the author in this study took the title " The Influence of the Family Environment and Student Learning Discipline on the Economic Learning Outcomes of Class XI Students at SMA Negeri 5 Pematang Siantar Academic Year 2023/2024."

THEORETICAL REVIEW

1. Learning Outcomes

Hamdani (2011:241) states that learning outcomes are changes in behavior obtained by students after experiencing learning activities. According to Susanto (2013: 5) "Changes that occur in students, both regarding cognitive, effective and psychomotor aspects, are the result of learning." Based on the opinions of experts regarding the meaning of learning outcomes above, the author can conclude that learning outcomes are results achieved by students during learning and learning activities, as well as evidence of success demonstrated in the cognitive, affective and psychomotor aspects shown in the form of symbols, letters, and sentences.

2. Environment Family

According to Hasbulloh (2013:38) that, "The family environment is the first educational environment, because it is in this family that children first receive education and guidance. It is also said to be the main environment, because most of a child's life is in the family, so education what children receive most is in the family." Thus it can be concluded that the environment is a learning resource that can be optimized to achieve the learning process.

3. Learning Discipline

According to Rose Mini (2011:7) Discipline is a guidance process aimed at instilling certain behavioral patterns, certain habits or forming humans with certain characteristics. Especially, which improves mental and moral quality. Based on the opinions above, it can be concluded that learning discipline is an attitude of obedience and obedience to rules that can hone students' skills and memory during the learning process. Apart from that, learning discipline can also be used as material for assessing affective aspects by teachers.

METHODS

Ex-post facto research because in this research no special treatment is made that manipulates the variables or subjects studied. This research is quantitative, meaning that all data is expressed in the form of numbers and the analysis is based on statistical analysis. This research includes correlation research, which aims to find a relationship between variables. This research was conducted at SMA N 5 Pematang Siantar Jalan Medan No.Km. 6.8, Tanjung Tongah, Tj. Tongah, District. Siantar Martoba, Pematang Siantar City, North Sumatra 21138 . This research was carried out at SMA N 5 Pematang Siantar in the odd semester of the 2023/2024 academic year . The population

in this study were all students of class XI SM A Negeri 5 Pematang Siantar 5 classes in total 172 students . The sample in this research was 102 students.

RESULT & DISCUSSION

Research Instrument Trial Results

Instrument Validity Test

Items that have a correlation value (r) > 0.361 are valid questionnaire items. Conversely, items that have a correlation value (r) < 0.361 are invalid questionnaire items. So it can be concluded that the validity test of the questionnaire instrument used in this research is valid.

Items that are declared valid are items that have a correlation value (r) > 0.361, while items that have a correlation value (r) < 0.361 are invalid items . This can be concluded that for the questions it is known that there are 15 items that have a correlation value (r) > 0.3 61 and as many as 6 questions (r) < 0.361, it is known that 14 questions have valid data and 1 is invalid. Therefore, 1 invalid question was replaced and tested again so that the questionnaire questions in this study were 15 questionnaire questions.

Instrument Reliability Test

For the questionnaire reliability criteria, if r count > r table with a significant level (α = 0.05) then the questionnaire is said to be reliable. However, if r count ≤ r table then the question is considered to have no reliability. If the Cronbach Alpha value is > 0.60 it is said to be reliable, but if the Cronbach Alpha value is < 0.60 it is said to be unreliable.

From the data obtained, 0.817 and 0.885, the r -table obtained = 0.361. So r-count > r-table and if the Cronbach Alpha value (0.817 and 885) > 0.361. From the results of calculating the reliability of the family environment and learning discipline, it can be concluded that the instruments in the questionnaire used are reliable.

Test Data Analysis Techniques

Data Normality Test

Table 1. Family environment normality test results

Xi	Fi	Fkum	Fs	Z	Ft	ft-fs	[ft-fs]
46	1	1	0,010	-2,801	0,003	-0,007	0,007
47	1	2	0,020	-2,649	0,004	-0,016	0,016
51	1	3	0,029	-2,038	0,021	-0,009	0,009
54	2	5	0,049	-1,580	0,057	-0,008	0,008
55	3	8	0,078	-1,427	0,077	-0,002	0,002
56	3	11	0,108	-1,274	0,102	-0,007	0,007
57	2	13	0,127	-1,121	0,131	-0,004	0,004
58	6	19	0,186	-0,969	0,166	-0,020	0,020
59	7	26	0,255	-0,816	0,207	-0,048	0,048
60	4	30	0,294	-0,663	0,254	-0,041	0,041
61	6	36	0,353	-0,511	0,305	-0,048	0,048
62	8	44	0,431	-0,358	0,360	-0,071	0,071

63	5	49	0,480	-0,205	0,419	-0,062	0,062
64	4	53	0,520	-0,052	0,479	-0,041	0,041
65	5	58	0,569	0,100	0,540	-0,029	0,029
66	7	65	0,637	0,253	0,600	-0,037	0,037
67	4	69	0,676	0,406	0,658	-0,019	0,019
68	2	71	0,696	0,558	0,712	0,016	0,016
69	3	74	0,725	0,711	0,762	0,036	0,036
70	6	80	0,784	0,864	0,806	0,022	0,022
71	3	83	0,814	1,017	0,845	0,032	0,032
72	3	86	0,843	1,169	0,879	-0,036	0,036
73	7	93	0,912	1,322	0,907	-0,005	0,005
74	3	96	0,941	1,475	0,930	-0,011	0,011
75	6	102	1	1,628	0,948	0,052	0,052
							0,675

1. Data stated distribute normal If significant > from 0.05 or 5%.
2. Data stated No distribute normal if significant < from 0.05.

Table 2. Learning Discipline Normality Test Results

Xi	Fi	Fkum	Fs	Z	Ft	ft-fs	[ft-fs]
45	1	1	0,010	-2,449	0,007	-0,003	0,003
46	1	2	0,020	-2,304	0,011	-0,009	0,009
50	3	5	0,049	-1,724	0,042	-0,007	0,007
51	2	7	0,069	-1,724	0,042	-0,026	0,026
52	2	9	0,088	-1,724	0,042	-0,046	0,046
53	7	16	0,157	-1,579	0,057	-0,100	0,100
54	2	18	0,176	-1,579	0,057	-0,119	0,119
55	3	21	0,206	-1,434	0,076	-0,130	0,130
56	3	24	0,235	-1,434	0,076	-0,160	0,160
57	3	27	0,265	-1,289	0,099	-0,166	0,166
58	6	33	0,324	-1,289	0,099	-0,225	0,225
59	3	36	0,353	-1,289	0,099	-0,254	0,254

60	7	43	0,422	-1,289	0,099	-0,323	0,323
61	3	46	0,451	-1,289	0,099	-0,352	0,352
62	7	53	0,520	-1,289	0,099	-0,421	0,421
63	6	59	0,578	-1,289	0,099	-0,480	0,480
64	4	63	0,618	-1,144	0,126	-0,491	0,491
65	5	68	0,667	-1,144	0,126	0,540	0,540
66	3	71	0,696	-0,999	0,159	0,537	0,537
67	5	76	0,745	-0,999	0,159	0,586	0,586
68	9	85	0,833	-0,999	0,159	0,674	0,674
69	3	88	0,863	-0,854	0,197	-0,666	-0,666
70	5	93	0,912	-0,854	0,197	-0,715	0,715
71	2	95	0,931	-0,854	0,197	-0,735	0,735
72	1	96	0,941	-0,709	0,239	-0,702	0,702
73	1	97	0,951	-0,709	0,239	-0,712	0,712
74	2	99	0,971	-0,709	0,239	-0,731	0,731
75	3	102	1,000	-0,564	0,286	-0,714	0,714

Data Multicollinearity Test

This multicollinearity test calculation is assisted by the VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) formula. If the independent variable experiences multicollinearity, then the VIF value is ≥ 10 or the independent variable does not experience multicollinearity if $VIF < 10$.

Table 3 Multicollinearity Test Results

Variables	VIF	Tolerance
Intercept	1.205329	0.829649

The assumption of Tolerance or Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) can be stated that if $VIF > 10$ or Tolerance value < 1.20 then multicollinearity is possible, or if $VIF < 10$ or Tolerance value > 0.10 then multicollinearity is not possible. It can be seen in the attachment, (1.20) that Tolerance > 0.10 or Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) < 10 , so it can be concluded that the data is not subject to symptoms of multicollinearity.

**Hypothesis testing
Multiple Linear Regression Test**

Table 4 . Multiple Linear Regression Test Results

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Intercept	51.86289022	44.67461234	1.160902972	0.255842812
X1	1.108169189	0.701158125	1.580483986	0.125641362
x2	-1.179524338	0.530504037	-2.223403134	0.03474871

The constant (a) value in table 4.7 is known to be 51.862, while the value from the family environment (X1) of 1.108 and the value of learning discipline (X2) as big as -1,179 so that The regression equation is:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_n X_n + e$$

$$Y = 51,862 + 1.108X_1 + -1.179X_2 + 20,838$$

1. A constant of 51.862 means that the variable has a consistent value results learning is 51,862.
 Coefficient regression X1 amounting to 1,179 And X2 as big as -1.108. Coefficient regression is positive, so it can be said that the direction of influence of the variable X1 and variables X2 with respect to Y is positive

Simple Linear Regression Test

1. Influence of Family Environment on student learning outcomes (X 1).
 The influence of the family environment on student learning outcomes is described by the regression equation = a + bX 1 where a and b can be calculated using the following formula:

$$a = \frac{(\sum Y)(\sum X_1^2) - (\sum X_1)(\sum X_1 Y)}{N(\sum X_1^2) - (\sum X_1)^2}$$

$$= \frac{(7524)(426657) - (6563)(483048)}{102(426657) - (6563)^2} = 89.50$$

$$b = \frac{N(\sum X_1 Y) - (\sum X_1)(\sum Y)}{N(\sum X_1^2) - (\sum X_1)^2}$$

$$= \frac{102(483048) - (6563)(7524)}{101(426657) - (6563)^2} = -0.24$$

From the results of the calculations a and b, the regression equation can be written as follows:

$$Y = 89.50 + -0.24 X 1$$

Thus the simple linear regression equation regarding the Family Environment students towards Economics learning outcomes class IX students of SMA Negeri 5 Pematangsiantar can be written using the linear regression equation as follows:
 = 89.50 + -0.24X 1 . This means that the Family Environment If a student has a score of 50, it is estimated that the student learning outcome score is Y = 89.50 + -0.24 (64) = 74.14 . Other scores can be calculated in the same way for each given X 1 score.

2. Student learning discipline on student learning outcomes (X 2)

Student learning discipline on student learning outcomes is described by the regression equation $Y = a + bX_2$ where a and b can be calculated using the following formula:

$$a = \frac{(\sum Y)(\sum X_2^2) - (\sum X_2)(\sum X_2 Y)}{N(\sum X_2^2) - (\sum X_2)^2}$$

$$= \frac{(12108)(507488) - (8902)(690870)}{157(507488) - (8902)^2} = 10.61$$

$$b = \frac{N(\sum X_2 Y) - (\sum X_2)(\sum Y)}{N(\sum X_2^2) - (\sum X_2)^2}$$

$$= \frac{102(463164) - (6313)(7524)}{102(395531) - (6313)^2} = 0.00715$$

From the results of the calculations a and b, the regression equation can be written as follows:

Thus, the simple linear regression equation regarding student learning discipline on Economics learning outcomes for class IX students at SMA Negeri 5 Pematangsiantar can be written as the following linear regression equation: $Y = 10.61 + 0.00715 X_2$. This means that if a student's learning discipline has a score of 50 then the estimated student learning outcome score is $Y = 10.61 + 0.00715 (50) = 11.06$. Other scores can be calculated in the same way for each given X_2 score.

Partial Test (t)

Table 5 . t Test Results

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Intercept	0.082765934	44.67461234	1.160902972	0.255842812
X1	1.108169189	0.701158125	1.580483986	0.125641362
x2	-1.179524338	0.530504037	-2.223403134	0.03474871

The hypotheses in this research are:

- Ho: $\beta = 0$: there is no significant influence
- Ha: $\beta \neq 0$: there is a significant influence. 0.0827

Simultaneous Hypothesis Test (F)

The F test is carried out to find out whether the independent variables together have an influence on the dependent variable. In this case, Fcount is compared with Ftable with the following conditions :

1. If F count > F table , then Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted
2. If F count < F table , then Ha is rejected and Ho is rejected.

Table 6 . F Test Results

ANOVA					
	<i>Df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	2	2376.742108	1188.371054	2.736518345	0.082765934
Residual	27	11725,12456	434.2638725		
Total	28	14101.86667			

Coefficient of Determination Test

Table 7 . Coefficient of Determination Test Results
 SUMMARY OUTPUTS

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.410537401
R Square	0.168540957
Adjusted R Square	0.106051399
Standard Error	20.83899884
Observations	30

The value of the coefficient of determination R Square in table 7 is known to be 0, which means that 16% of the family environment variables or learning discipline have an influence on student learning outcomes at SMA Negeri 5 Pematang Siantar and 84% are the influence of other variables not examined in this observation.

Discussion

Based on the data analysis that has been carried out, the research process shows the research findings. From the description of the research data, the following data was obtained:

To see whether there is a relationship between variable Y and X differentiate based on a simple linear regression equation $= 89.50 + - 0.24X$. Meanwhile, to see the magnitude of the influence between these variables, it can be seen from a simple correlation test which is expressed as "R". The results of the hypothesis test are.

There is a significant influence between the influence of the family environment and learning discipline on the economic learning outcomes of students in class XI at SMA Negeri 5 Pematang Siantar FY 2023/2024 . This means that the influence of the family environment is sufficient then student learning outcomes are sufficient and vice versa. Meanwhile, the magnitude of the influence between these two variables means that the influence on students' learning discipline is sufficient.

The influence of the family environment and learning discipline on learning outcomes jointly influences learning outcomes. These results can be seen in the F test where the calculated F value (2.736) > table F value (1.77). The assumption of Tolerance or Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) is capable stated that If VIF > 10 or mark Tolerance < 1.20 so that capable multicollinearity., or If VIF < 10 or mark Tolerance >0.10 so it is not capable of multicollinearity. Can be seen in the attachment, (1.20) that Tolerance > 0.10 or Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) < 10, so that capable concluded that data No capable symptom multicollinearity.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

There are several conclusions made by researchers based on the research results that have been researched and discussed in the previous chapter , namely as follows:

1. There is a positive and significant influence of study habits on learning outcomes. This result can be seen in the t test where the t value of the family environment (0.125) > t table value (1.697) which means this variable is significant.
2. There is a positive and significant influence of learning concentration on learning outcomes. This result can be seen in the t test where the t value of learning discipline (0.034) > t table value (1.697) which means that this variable is significant.
3. Environment and learning discipline jointly influence learning outcomes, these results can be seen in the F test where the Fcount value (2.736) > Ftable value (0.361). The R Square coefficient of determination test was found to be 0.168, which means that 16%9 of family environment variables and learning discipline have an influence on student learning outcomes at SMA Negeri 5 Pematang Siantar, and the remaining 83.1% is the influence of variables not examined in this research.

FURTHER STUDY

As part of the conclusion of this observation, the observer made the following suggestions :

1. The family environment and student learning discipline have a positive or relevant influence on learning outcomes at SMA Negeri 5 Pematang Siantar for the 2023/2024 academic year. Therefore, improving student learning outcomes requires paying attention to these two factors so that learning achievement at school is optimal.
2. Student learning outcomes . If in the future someone makes a similar observation, it should be carried out in the same place

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REFERENCES

- Ahmad Slamet. 2007. Human Resource Management. Semarang:
- Anas Salahudin, Irwanto Alkriencichie, 2013. Character Education, Bandung : CV Pustaka Setia
- Ahiri, J. 2017. Authentic Assessment in Learning, (Jakarta: Uhamka Press, p. 18.
- Darmadi. (2017). Development of a Learning Method Model in Student Learning Dynamics. Yogyakarta: Deepublish.
- Ministry of National Education 2003. Republic of Indonesia Law No.20 of 2003 concerning the system | | | National Education.
- Daryanto and Suryatri, Darmiatun, 2013. Character Education in Schools. Yogyakarta: Gava Media.
- Dalyono, M. (2012). Psychology Jakarta: Rineka. Education
- Fitriani. 2016. The influence of learning motivation and discipline on students' social studies learning outcomes at Karya Indah Middle School, Tapung District. PeKA Journal. 4(2).2337- 652X
- Hamdani. (2011). Teaching and Learning Strategies. Bandung: Faithful Library.
- Hamdani. 2017. Teaching and Learning Strategies. Bandung: Pustaka Setia
- Hasbull o h. 2013. Basics of Education. Jakarta: PT Rajagrafindo Persada Helmawati.
- (2014). Family Education. Bandung: Rosdakarya Youth.
- Istarani & Intan Pulungan. 2015. Encyclopedia of Education. Medan: Media Persada
- Kuncoro Wahyu. 2020. Student Discipline Development, Central Jakarta (Ministry of Education and Culture 2020).
- Compri. (2017), Learning and the Factors That Influence It. Yogyakarta: Media Academ
- Marijan (2016). Children's Education Methods to Build the Character of Children who are Virtuous, Intelligent and Achievement, Sabda Media Team.
- Mini Rose. (2011). Discipline in Children, Central Jakarta (Ministry of National Education).

- Nasution. 2011. Various Approaches to the Learning & Teaching Process. Jakarta: PT Bumi Aksara
- Sudjana, Nana.2010.Research on Learning Process Results and types.Bandung:pt.Remaja Rosdakarya
- Parwati, Ni Nyoman, I Putu Suryawan and Ratih Ayu Apsari. (2018). Learning and Learning. Depok: PT Raja Grafindo Persada
- Rusmono. (2017). Learning Strategies with Problem Based Learning are Necessary (Second Edition). Bogor. Ghalia Indonesia
- Rusman. (2013). Factors that influence learning outcomes. Jakarta: PT. Aksar Earth
- Slameto. 2010. Learning and the factors that influence it. Jakarta: PT. Rineka Cipta
- Susanto.2013 Learning and Learning Theory. Jakarta. The main son's charisma
- Sugiyono, (2021). QUANTITATIVE QUALITATIVE RESEARCH METHODS and R&D (M.Dr. Ir. Sutopo, S.Pd (ed); 2nd ed)
- Sugiyono. (2017). Quantitative, Qualitative, and R&D Research Methods. Bandung: Alfabeta, CV. (2017). Quantitative, Qualitative, and R&D Research Methods. Bandung: Alfabeta, CV. (2017). Quantitative, Qualitative, and R&D Research Methods. Bandung: Alfabeta, CV.(2019). Quantitative, Qualitative, and R&D Research Methods. Bandung: Alfabeta. (2016). Quantitative Research Methods. Qualitative and R&D. Bandung: PT Alfabeta. (2014). Educational Research Methods Quantitative Qualitative Approach, and R&D. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Wibowo. 2012. Performance Management Third Edition, Sixth Printing, PT. Raja Grafindo Persada, Jakarta.